

PALEOGEOGRAPHIC RECONSTRUCTIONS OF THE ARGENTINE ISLANDS REGION BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF SPATIAL AND FACIES VARIABILITY OF BOTTOM SEDIMENTS

S. Kadurin, G. Pedan, S. Shatalyn, A. Kuzmenko, O. Kuzmenko.

Odesa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Odesa, Ukraine; kadurins@gmail.com

The section of modern seafloor sediments nearby the Antarctic Peninsula is a valuable archive of Earth's climate history, providing essential understanding of natural climate variability and the potential consequences of human-induced climate change. The record of climate variability in seafloor sediments around Antarctica has a global importance, as changes in the Southern Hemisphere can affect the entire Earth's climate system. Understanding of Antarctic climate trends from past to the present provides critical context for interpreting modern climate change and its potential impacts at the global level.

As a result of our research, the following conclusions were obtained. The exit from the last glaciation in the area of the Argentine Islands took place gradually. This process reflected in the peculiarities of the underwater relief and the section of bottom sediments. In general, the modern underwater relief is the result of different endogenous and exogenous processes interaction. The magmatic activity, starting from the Jurassic period, and modern tectonic movements along the active suture zone in the Antarctic Peninsula area caused the formation of the fault-block system of the research area. This led to the fact that the deepest depressions were formed along the main rupture faults. The smaller order faults and zones of fracturing turned into channels and depressions between the islands. Exogenous processes were primarily associated with glaciation and warming, which was reflected in the formation of significant glacial flows and the development of exaration along submarine valleys and channels. As a result, the presence of valleys with relatively flat and wide bottoms and steep slopes is typical in the modern relief.

Lithologically, muddy silts with admixtures of sand and crystalline rocks fragments represent the bottom sediments in the Penola Strait area. Seventy species of diatoms were identified in bottom sediments from Penola Strait. The distribution of diatoms has clear patterns that are associated with the properties of surface waters and the duration of sea ice cover. According to biogeographic and ecological characteristics, a significant percentage of diatoms from the Penola Strait sediments are pelagic taxa of the open ocean, typical for this region as a whole. Among them, cold-water species that live in the open ocean near the ice edge predominate.

Reconstructions of the facies settings and distribution of bottom sediments in the Argentine Islands area showed that a significant ice sheet, which completely occupied the study area at the time of its maximum development approximately 26 thousand years ago, marked the last glacial period. The Argentine Islands area became ice-free approximately 10,000 to 7,000 years ago. The subsequent melting occurred gradually with stages of deceleration and acceleration. Sometimes even reverse moments of increasing the amount of ice and decreasing the ambient temperature were observed.